

Isolation of bacteria resistant to Ni and Pb from shrimp samples and other biodegrading bacteria from sea water

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Abstract

This investigation explored bacteria species inhabiting general, basic marine environments and also in moderately polluted environments with the presence of the heavy metals nickel (Ni) and lead (Pb) in order to identify species with the ability to counter the effects of pollution. There were 2 major objectives of this study. First, to assess random species of bacteria found in the ocean and identify any species that exhibit the ability to mitigate pollution, both organic and inorganic. Second, to determine if any species of bacteria parasitic on aquatic animals can tolerate Ni and Pb concentrations of 6.25 µg/mL. The samples were subjected to inoculation and culture, selection, PCR, and Sanger sequencing. DNA sequences were identified using the National Center for Biotechnology Information Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (NCBI BLAST). Bacteria in prawn blood was identified as *Lactococcus garvieae* (*L. Garvieae*); a yellow colony from sea water was identified as *Alloalcanivorax xenomutans* (*A. xenomutans*); a red colony from sea water was identified as *Roseivivax halotolerans* (*R. halotolerans*). The isolation of *L. Garvieae* from heavy metal selective medium indicates that it is resistant to heavy metals, and thus this pathogenic bacteria may out-compete other symbiotic bacteria where there are high concentrations of heavy metals, and cause disease in the prawns in these conditions.

1. Introduction

The ocean is known for its unlimited diversity, and marine ecosystems are home to a vast array of bacterial species, many of which play crucial roles in biochemical cycles such as nutrient recycling and organic matter decomposition. With industrial progress over the past century, conditions in the ocean have been altered by the release of pollutants into seawater. In response, microorganisms present in seawater have developed adaptations to these changes, which have often helped ocean ecosystems mitigate the effects of pollution. As such, biologists around

the world began to investigate the use of bacteria to mitigate environmental pollution. For example, some biologists focused on species of bacteria that thrive around areas of oil spills, such as *Alcanivorax*, *Pseudomonas*, *Marinobacter*, and *Rhodococcus*, which likely have the ability to decompose pollutant oil spills into CO₂ and water [1]. Other biologists focused on bacteria inhabiting sponge layers that produce extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) that can bind to metals and organic pollutants, and thus remove them from water [2].

This study focuses on heavy metal contamination in fresh water, and forms of organic pollution in marine environments; both have become very serious problems. Heavy metal ions disrupt ecosystems, contaminate seafood sources, and cause cellular disorders in humans [3][4]. In order to address this issue and add new information to the literature and research of these topics, this study was designed to isolate bacteria from random samples of sea water, and from a fresh water prawn that is susceptible to heavy metal contamination. The other objective of the study is to identify species of bacteria that can endure high concentrations of heavy metals, and also species that can degrade organic wastes. Identification of these types of bacteria may lead to the development of bacterial species that can mitigate heavy metal and organic waste contamination in water ecosystems, and thus reduce pollution in our environments.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Bacteria cultivation-Sea Water

2.1.1 Sampling

The first part of the experiment used seawater collected from Dapeng Bay, (22.56140° N, 114.46649° E) in Shenzhen, China. The seawater samples were collected in

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autoclaved 50 mL Eppendorf (EP) tubes, and were stored at 4°C until use.

2.1.2 Inoculate sea water samples on Petri dishes:

A 50 µL drop of seawater was placed on a Petri dish containing Marin Agar 2216 (Hope Bio, Qingdao). The drop of seawater was then spread evenly across the plate using a spreading rod until friction was felt on the surface. Once the seawater was thoroughly spread, the Petri dish was sealed to ensure proper incubation conditions. The sealed Petri dishes were incubated overnight at 28°C.

2.1.3 Purification of bacteria species

The double-pipette tip method was used to purify bacteria that grew on the Petri dishes. A 1,000 µL pipette tip was used to handle the smaller-sized pipette tip. The Petri dishes were retrieved from the 28°C incubator, and 3 bacterial colonies with bright colors were selected. The pipette heads were dipped into the selected bacteria colonies, and then the pipette heads were used to inoculate another set of plates with the same medium by scratching. The scratching was done in a zigzag pattern, starting with horizontal streaks up to half of the plate, and then it was continued vertically, completing 2 vertical regions of inoculation. This process was repeated 3 times for all of the samples. Purification was repeated until only one colony was present for each sample.

2.2. Bacteria cultivation *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*

2.2.1 Preparation and production of plates

A modified Lysogeny *broth* (LB) medium was used for this part of the study. The LB medium was prepared by adding 2.5 g of LB powder, 0.5 g of NaCl, 1 g of glucose, and 1.5 g of agar powder into 100 mL of water in a 250 mL medium bottle. The bottles were then autoclaved at 121°C at atmospheric pressure plus 0.1 MPa for 30 minutes. For the selective medium, heavy metal solutions of Ni and Pb at a concentration of 1,000 µg/mL were filtered through filter paper with a pore size of 0.22 µm. Next, 4 µL, 2 µL, and 1 µL of the Pb and Ni solutions, respectively, were added to corresponding empty EP tubes. Subsequently, 20 mL of the basic medium was added to each tube, and the contents were mixed by shaking three times. The resulting mixture was then poured onto Petri dishes and allowed to cool.

2.2.2 Sampling

The second part of the experiment used Giant River Prawns, *M. rosenbergii*, that were purchased from local seafood markets in Guangdong, China. The prawns were dissected, and their intestines, digestive glands, and blood samples were collected. The samples were placed into 2,000

µL EP tubes filled with 1,000 µL of double-distilled water (ddH₂O), mixed thoroughly using a vibrating pen, and stored at 4°C until needed.

2.2.3 Bacteria inoculation and purification

A 50 µL sample of the liquid was extracted from the 2,000 µL EP tubes, and placed onto Petri dishes with a selective medium containing Ni and Pb ions at 6.25 µg/mL. The liquid drop was spread evenly over the Petri dish using a spreading rod, and the Petri dishes were sealed with biofilms to prevent contamination. Following the same protocols as for sea water, the process was repeated to purify a selected white bacterial colony.

2.3. DNA extraction from isolated and purified bacteria

The plates containing grown, purified bacteria colonies were taken out of the incubator. A 2,000 µL EP tube was prepared for each sample. 100 µL of double distilled water was added to each EP tube. The sealed plates were opened, and a pipette with a medium tip was used to scrape a visible solid piece of the bacterial colony from the plate onto the pipette tip. The solid was transferred into one of the EP tubes by stirring, and any remaining bacteria on the tip were blown into the tube with the pipette. The final mixture was stirred multiple times. The tubes were labeled with the corresponding plate numbers and sealed, and the plates were resealed. The EP tubes were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until use. The plates were put back into the incubators in case of future need.

2.4. PCR

The previously prepared EP tubes were heated for 10 minutes at 100°C, and then centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant liquid of the centrifuged sample was collected as the DNA sample. Seven PCR tubes were prepared by adding 1 µL of 1492r primer, 1 µL of 27f primer, 12.5 µL of DNA polymerase, 7.5 µL of double-distilled water (ddH₂O), and 3 µL of the final DNA sample for each sample. The PCR tubes were spun in a mini centrifuge to ensure that no liquid remained on the walls of the tubes. The centrifuged tubes were then placed into the PCR machine, and the temperature ranges were set: First, the temperature goes to 95°C for two minutes. Then a cycle starts and repeats 30-35 times with 95°C for 10 seconds, 60°C for 10-15 seconds, and 72°C for 1.5 minutes. Finally, when the cycles are over, the machine first maintains temperature at 72°C for a final extension for 1-5 minutes and then returns to 4 degrees to preserve the PCR product at last. The PCR process was started, and it was allowed to run until completion.

Figure 1: Sea water bacteria inoculation on basic 2216 medium: A-inoculation as a whole B-Green colony bacteria from inoculation C-Red colony of bacteria from inoculation D-Yellow colony of bacteria from inoculation

2.5. Gel preparation and electrophoresis

In general, 25 mL of tris-acetate-EDTA (TAE) buffer with 1.5% agarose was used for a small amount of gel. The agarose powder was added to the TAE buffer, and the mixture was stirred until the agarose was evenly dispersed throughout the TAE buffer. The solution was then heated twice to ensure that the agarose completely dissolved. Once the solution had cooled to a warm temperature, 1.25 μL of nucleic acid dye per 25 mL of TAE was added, and the solution was stirred thoroughly.

The solution was poured into a gel box of an appropriate size, and a comb was inserted to create holes in the gel. After the gel had solidified, 5 μL of marker (DNA loading buffer) was inserted into the first well of the gel, followed by 5 μL of each sample into the wells of the other columns. Electrophoresis was then performed at 120 volts for approximately 25 minutes. After electrophoresis was completed, the markers were examined to determine which PCR samples had developed products. The successful samples, numbers 2, 4, and 6 were sent to a company for DNA Sanger sequencing.

2.6. BLAST analysis and species identification

The resulting DNA sequence obtained from DNA sequencing was subjected to a blast search against the NCBI nucleotide (nt) database. Species identity was determined with the percentage ID of the query sequence over 98 percent with the matched bacterial species 16s rDNA sequence.

Figure 2: Prawn samples inoculated on selective LB medium with Ni and Pb concentrations at 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ or 3.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. A) Prawn intestine sample inoculated on selective medium with Ni concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. B) Prawn blood sample inoculated on selective medium with Ni concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. C) Prawn intestine sample inoculated on selective medium with Pb concentration of 3.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. D) Bacteria from prawn blood grown on LB medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

3. Results

3.1. Bacteria Inoculation from sea water with Basic MA medium

For samples from sea water, we performed bacteria inoculation, with 100 times dilution with ddH₂O on Marine agar 2216 medium. (Fig. 1-A) In the sample, at least three types of bacteria colonies can be observed. One type with circular form, relative medium size, flat elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, completely opaque and in dark green color. (Fig. 1-B) Second type with irregular form, relative small size, raised elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, relatively opaque and in pink-white color. (Fig. 1-C) The third type with circular form, relative small size, raised elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, completely opaque and in bright yellow color. (Fig. 1-D)

3.2. Bacteria Inoculation from prawn intestine with selective LB medium of Ni with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$

Undiluted samples from the prawn intestine were inoculated onto selective LB medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Only one type of bacterial colony was observed after culture. The colony had an irregular form, a relatively large size, had raised elevation, entire margins, a smooth surface, and was relatively opaque and white (Fig. 2-A).

3.3. Bacteria from prawn blood grown on LB lead medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$

Undiluted samples from prawn blood were inoculated onto selective LB medium with a Pb concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Only one type of bacterial colony was observed after culture. The colony had a regular form, relatively small size, raised elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, and a relatively transparent white color (Fig. 2-B).

Figure 3: Purification of Sea water bacteria colonies on basic 2216 medium: A-green colonies from sea water sample inoculation B-Red colonies from sea water sample inoculation C-Yellow colonies from sea water sample inoculation

Figure 4: Purification of prawn sample bacterial colonies on selective LB medium with different concentrations of Ni and Pb. A) Prawn intestine sample purification cultivated on LB selective medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. B) Prawn blood sample purification cultivated on LB selective medium with a Pb concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. C) Prawn intestine sample purification cultivated on LB selective medium with a Pb concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. D) Prawn blood sample purification cultivated on LB selective medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL.

3.4. Bacteria from prawn intestine grown on LB lead medium with heavy metal concentration at 3.15 µg/mL

Undiluted prawn intestine samples were inoculated onto selective LB medium with Pb at a concentration of 3.15 µg/mL. Only one type of bacterial colony was observed after culture. The colony had an irregular form, a relatively large size, raised elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, and was a relatively opaque white color (Fig. 2-C).

3.5. Bacteria from prawn blood grown on LB Nickel medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 µg/mL

Undiluted prawn blood was inoculated onto selective LB medium containing a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. Only one type of bacterial colony was observed. The colony had an irregular form, had a relatively small size, had raised elevation, entire margins, smooth surface, and was relatively transparent and white (Fig. 2-D).

3.6. Purification of Green Bacteria colony from Sea water grown on basic MA medium

Small portions of the green bacterial colony were extracted from the Marine Agar 2216 mixed medium, and purified by culture on another Petri dish of Marine Agar 2216 medium. After culture, only the green colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had flat elevations, circular forms, and entire margins. The surface was rough, and the colonies were completely opaque and dark green (Fig. 3-A).

3.7. Purification of Red Bacteria colony from Sea water grown on basic MA medium

Small portions of the red bacterial colony were extracted from the Marine Agar 2216 mixed medium, and purified by culture on another Petri dish of Marine Agar 2216 medium. After culture, only the red colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had flat elevations, irregular forms, and entire margins. The surface of the purified colonies was rough, and they were a relatively transparent red color (Fig. 3-B).

3.8. Purification of yellow Bacteria colony from Sea water grown on basic MA medium

Small portions of the yellow bacterial colony were extracted from the Marine Agar 2216 mixed medium, and purified by culture on another Petri dish of Marine Agar 2216 medium. After culture, only the yellow colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had a flat elevation, irregular form, and entire margins. The surface of the colonies was rough, they were a relatively opaque yellow color (Fig. 3-C).

3.9. Purification of Bacteria colony from prawn intestine grown on LB Nickel medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 µg/mL

Small portions of the white colony were extracted from the mixed LB medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL and purified onto another Petri dish of the same medium. After culture, only the white colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had raised elevation, irregular form, and undulated margins. The surface of the colonies was rough, and they were an opaque white color (Fig. 4-A).

3.10. Purification of Bacteria from prawn blood grown on LB lead medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 µg/mL

Small portions of the white colony were extracted from the mixed LB medium with a Pb concentration at 6.25 µg/mL and purified to another Petri dish of the same medium. After culture, only the white colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had raised elevation, irregular form, and undulated margins. The surface of the colonies was rough, and the colonies were an opaque white color (Fig. 4-B).

3.11. Purification of Bacteria from prawn intestine grown on LB lead medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 µg/mL

Small portions of the white colony were extracted from the mixed LB medium with lead concentration at 6.25 µg/mL and purified on another Petri dish of the same medium. After culture, only the white colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had a raised elevation, irregular form, and undulated margins. The surface of the colonies was rough, and the colonies were an opaque white color (Fig. 4-C).

3.12. purification of Bacteria from prawn blood grown on LB Nickle medium with heavy metal concentration at 6.25 µg/mL

Small portions of the white colony were extracted from the mixed LB medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL and purified onto another Petri dish of the same medium. After culture, only the white colony bacteria were observed (successful purification). The purified bacteria occupied the whole Petri dish in zigzag lines. The colonies had raised elevation, irregular form, and undulated margins. The surface of the purified colonies was rough, and they were an opaque white color (Fig. 4-D).

3.13. Bacterial isolates and their species identity

After performing PCR on the purified samples as previously described, the PCR products were subjected to gel electrophoresis. There were 8 holes in the gel; the first hole was filled with markers and the others with PCR products. Successful electrophoresis was only identified in the third, fifth, and seventh holes. Hole 3 contained prawn blood cultivated on selective LB medium with a Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. The sample for this hole is species *Lactococcus garvieae*. Hole 5 contained the yellow colony bacteria cultivated from sea water. The sample for this hole is the species *Alcanivorax xenomutans*. Hole 7 contained the red colony bacteria cultivated from sea water. The sample for this hole is species *Roseivivax halotolerans*. Pictures and

Figure 5: Electrophoresis

Figure 6: Sequencing results for *L. garvieae* samples with 27F primer: A. 1-250 Base Pair B. 250-520 Base Pair C. 520-780 Base Pair D. 620-890 Base Pair

the table below show the results in detail (Fig. 5, Table.1).

3.14. Sequencing results for *Lactococcus garvieae* sample

Pictures are shown for sequencing of the sample for 27F (Fig. 6) and for 1492R primers (Fig. 7). Sequencing graphs and base pairs have been shown.

3.15. Sequencing results for *Alcanivorax xenomutans* sample

Pictures are shown for sequencing of the sample for 27F (Fig. 8) and for 1492R primers (Fig. 9). Sequencing graphs and base pairs have been shown.

Table 1: Sample Test Results

Sample	Test Type	Error	Product Info	Species	Similarity
shrimp bld	27F	Double peak, possible deletion mutation	SZ0715 Z1.27F.30085512.A11.ab1		
shrimp bld	1492R		SZ0715 Z1.1492R.30085513.A12.ab1	<i>Lactococcus garvieae</i>	99%
sea yellow	27F		SZ0715 Z2.27F.30085514.B01.ab1		
sea yellow	1492R		SZ0715 Z2.1492R.30085515.B02.ab1	<i>Alcanivorax xenomutans</i>	99%
sea red	27F		SZ0715 Z3.27F.30085516.B03.ab1		
sea red	1492R		SZ0715 Z3.1492R.30085517.B04.ab1	<i>Roseivivax halotolerans</i>	99%

Figure 7: Sequencing results for *L. garvieae* samples with 1492R primer: A.1-230 Base Pair B.230-460 Base Pair C.460-690 Base Pair D. 690-890 Base Pair

Figure 8: Sequencing results for *A. xenomutans* samples with 27F primer: A.1-230 Base Pair B. 230-460 Base Pair C. 460-690 Base Pair D. 690-890 Base Pair

3.16. Sequencing results for *Roseivivax halotolerans* sample

Pictures are shown for sequencing of the sample for 27F(Fig.10) and for 1492R(Fig.11) primers. Sequencing graphs and base pairs have been shown.

4. Discussion

4.1. Selective medium concentration setting

During the preliminary phase of this project, the Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research was consulted to identify heavy metal-resistant bacteria. The study referenced described how scientists isolated heavy metal-resistant bacteria using a selective medium with a Pb concentration of

Figure 9: Sequencing results for *A. xenomutans* with 1492R primer: A. 1-230 B. 230-460 Base Pair C. 460-690 Base pair D. 690-890 base pairs

Figure 10: Sequencing results for *R. halotolerans* with 27F primer: A. 1-230 Base Pair B. 230-460 Base Pair C.460-690 Base Pair D. 690-890 Base Pair

Figure 11: Sequencing results for *R. halotolerans* with 1492R primer: A. 1-230 Base Pair B. 230-460 Base Pair C.460-690 Base Pair D. 690-890 Base Pair

300 µg/mL [5]. However, the referenced study used samples collected from an industrial waste site, a waste lake beside a Tannery. In comparison, this project was based on samples from natural environments and aquaculture sites at which there are no direct signs of heavy metal contamination. In order to identify appropriate conditions for this study, several preliminary tests were performed. First, instead of an initial concentration of 300 µg/mL, this study tested initial concentrations 30 µg/mL, 15 µg/mL, and 7.5 µg/mL; cultivation of bacteria failed at all 3 concentrations. A second attempt was made with concentrations of 15 µg/mL, 7.5 µg/mL, and 3.75 µg/mL, and bacteria only grew on the Petri dish with a concentration of 3.5 µg/mL. Based on this result, concentrations of 6.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 6.0 µg/mL were tested, and bacteria grew when the concentration was 6.25 µg/mL or lower. Thus, 6.25 µg/mL was chosen as the optimal maximum concentration for this study.

4.2. Isolation of bacteria from the blood of the fresh water prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*

The species of bacteria isolated from the blood of *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* was *Lactococcus garvieae*. This bacteria is Gram negative, it is a common pathogen that infects fish and cause the disease lactococcosis, which is a disease of blood cells that has a high mortality in fish aquaculture [6, 7]. Compared to the diversity of bacterial colonies cultivated from sea water, cultivation of blood from *M. rosenbergii* resulted in uniform colonies of *L. garvieae*. This indicates that in environments with high concentrations of heavy metals where normal symbiotic bacteria in prawns might not be able to survive, *L. garvieae* can. Thus, we might hypothesize that *M. rosenbergii* are more likely to lose their immunity and spread lactococcosis disease in environments with high concentrations of Pb or Ni. Identification of *L. garvieae* in aquaculture systems may serve as an indicator of contamination and an increased risk of lactococcosis. In addition to the identification of *L. garvieae* in prawn blood, this bacteria also has other meaningful applications in the field of medication. Although *L. garvieae* is pathogenic in aquaculture, it was previously examined as having probiotic functions in certain mammals. A study that isolated *L. garvieae* from Mongolian sheep discovered that it has the probiotic functions of maintaining intestinal mucous barrier integrity and protecting against food borne *Clostridium perfringens* infection[8]. The probiotic nature of the bacteria can be further explored in humans, and it may lead to the development of drugs to treat food poisoning[9].

4.3. Yellow colony bacteria isolated from sea water

The yellow colony bacteria isolated from sea water was identified as *Alloalcanivorax xenomutans*. It is a Gram-negative bacteria that is halophilic and plays a role in biodegradation. It has the ability to degrade hydrocarbons, par-

ticularly in oil-contaminated environments. This discovery indicates the potential of the marine ecosystem to respond to organic pollutants. Based on this finding, it may be possible to develop *A. xenomutans* into a product that can be added to polluted areas to degrade harmful chemicals without an obvious drawback, as no studies have found that it is pathogenic to humans or aquatic life. Notably, studies have been examining *A. xenomutans* and the enzymes it to degrade polyester compounds in the ocean [10].

4.4. Red colony bacteria isolated from sea water

The red colony bacteria isolated from sea water was identified as *Roseivivax halotolerans*. It is a Gram negative bacteria that is known to be able to survive harsh conditions, such as high salinity. The presence of this bacteria in the sea water sample is normal, since sea water has a higher salinity than soils used for previous studies of *R. halotolerans*. There is minimal literature discussing the potential applications of this bacteria. However, future studies may focus on the use of this bacteria to improve soil conditions in places with high salinity, which can allow the cultivation of crops in previously undesirable areas [11].

5. Conclusion

This study produced a number of noteworthy results *L. garvieae* is a species of bacteria that infects marine animals and is pathogenic, while it may provide probiotic functions in humans. It was isolated from the blood of *M. rosenbergii* using selective LB medium with a Pb or Ni concentration of 6.25 µg/mL. This suggests that *L. garvieae* is resistant to heavy metal pollution and that it can survive when there is a high concentration of heavy metals, and that bacteria that are symbiotic in prawns may not be able to survive resulting in *L. garvieae* being a pathogen. *A. xenomutans*, a species of bacteria known for its ability to degrade microplastics, was isolated from water from Dapeng Bay and appeared as yellow bacterial colonies. Follow-up studies could focus on the application of this bacterial species to degrade wastes as it is developed into environmental friendly products. Also isolated from Dapeng Bay water was *R. halotolerans*, a bacteria known for its ability to survive high salinity, which appeared as red colonies on culture. It has the potential to be developed into a product that can reduce high levels of salinity in soils, and thus make the soil suitable to cultivate crops.

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